

Analysis over distribution of water-associated infectious diseases all over India.

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Abstract:

Available potable water in majority of cities and villages of India is grossly inadequate to meet the increasing demands for water each year due to rapid population growth. Hence, the population often results into sourcing water from questionable water points. During the dry season, which often coincides with dry public taps, urban and rural dwellers utilize water collected from alternative sources such as boreholes, wells, streams, lakes, rivers and reservoirs for domestic uses.

On the other hand cities and villages reinforced with abundance of water struggle to manage the water efficiently, often leading to water collecting in potholes and or in the surrounding areas and going unused. This can have severe consequences as water-borne diseases, such as cholera, malaria and diarrhoea can spread as a result of improper management of the water supply as well as discharge.

The overall goal of our study is to explore the possible relationship between distribution of water-associated infectious diseases all over India and socio-environmental and demographic factors. Looking at the figures, the Ganges provide water to over 500 million Indians - contamination of just one source of water could affect millions of lives in one go. Water contamination often occurs due to inadequate and incompetent management of resources as well as inflow of sewage into the source. It is reported that groundwater in one-third of India's 600 districts is not fit for drinking as the concentration of fluoride, iron, salinity and arsenic exceeds the tolerance levels. About 65 million people have been suffering from fluorosis, a crippling disease due to a high amount of fluoride, and five million are suffering from arsenicosis in West Bengal due to high amount of arsenic. A World Resources Report says: about 70 per cent of India's water supply is seriously polluted with sewage effluents.

There is still concern about the availability of fresh and good quality drinking water to all Indians. If water supply, sanitation, hygiene and water resource management can be improved than at least 10 per cent of diseases worldwide could be avoided.

Keywords: Water, Infectious, Diseases

1.Introduction:

India is a land of diversity .Huge contrast in water availability and scarcity can be experienced all over country. It is a matter of concern that 600 million people in India face high to extreme water stress because of limited availability of water resources and rising demand of water. About 3/4 of households in the country do not have drinking water facility in their premise which results into sourcing water from contaminated water points.

Water contamination is determined by presence of inorganic substance or pathogenic microorganism in water which adversely affect man's health, caused by sewerage and industrial effluents, surface run-off and many anthropogenic activities that alter the physical (colour, taste, and smell) and chemical characteristics of water.

Waterborne disease are any illness caused by the use of contaminated water either directly or through food; and by the of contaminated water for the purpose of personal hygiene and recreation[1]. Over past decade water related health issues has become increasingly comprehensive, with the emergence of new water related diseases and reemergence of one's already known.

Diseases associated with drinking water is due to pathogens, which include viruses, bacteria, and protozoa, which spread via the oral-fecal route[2]. These diseases are more prevalent in areas with poor sanitary conditions. *Campylobacter jejuni*, *Microsporidia*, *Yersinia enterocolitica*, *Cyclospora*, *Caliciviruses*, and environmental bacteria like *Mycobacterium sp.*, *Aeromonas sp.*, *Legionella pneumophila*, and multidrug-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* have been associated with waterborne illnesses. These pathogens travel through water sources and interfuse directly through persons handling food and water. The main distribution of many water-borne pathogens varies substantially from one country to another. Some pathogens such as *Vibrio cholerae*, Hepatitis E virus, and Schistosomiasis are restricted to certain tropical countries; others, such as Cryptosporidiosis and Campylobacteriosis, are probably widespread.

Rotavirus infections predominate in the winter months and cause for approximately 140 million cases/year with 600,000–800,000 deaths/year [3]. Evidence on *Entamoebahistolytica* in children (Dhaka, Bangladesh), the causative agent of Amoebiasis (Amoebic dysentery), shows that infection occurred in 80 percentage of children over a four-year period with a re-infection rate of 53 percentage [4]. According to WHO records of infectious disease outbreaks in 132 countries from 1998 to 2001, outbreaks of waterborne diseases are at the top of the list, with cholera as the most frequent disease, followed by acute diarrhea and typhoid fever [5].

Provision to safe drinking water is of great concern in most of developing countries [6]. Access to basic facilities like clean water supply and better sanitation is necessary to prevent from waterborne disease as waterborne diseases and illness has increased the cost of medicinal facilities and poverty among rural communities [7].

2. Literature review:

Shailesh Sutariya, et.al,(2001-2002), studied prevalence of diarrheal disease amongst under five population revealed that 81.88% infants and 70.70% children of 1-5-year of age group were affected from diarrheal disease in village of Dhinoj and half of diarrheal cases occurred in monsoon season[8].

Beryl P. Gladstone, et. al, (2009), surveyed morbidity rate in the first three year children in an Indian Slum results showed that morbidity rate was 11.26% per year. Children suffered from gastrointestinal illness (2%) during hot /dry season (March to June), acute respiratory illness(58%) in wet/cold season (October to January), diarrhea(18%), ear infection(7%), skin related problem(4%)[9].

Brijesh C.Purohit, (2012), studied health impact of waterborne disease and regional disparities in India and suggested that efficient health outcome could be achieved by better management of existing programs, innovative measures and participation of community as diarrhea and typhoid cases has increased due to physical and biological contamination. Malaria was caused due to lack of drainage facilities. Cases of ARI covers area with inadequate sanitation facilities. Safe water supply reduces the cases of Hepatitis [10].

V.S. Saravanan, et. al, (2012), analyzed waterborne disease in Ahemdabad revealed that chance of being infected increases where households are not aware of personal hygiene, receive poor water quality, had poor housing and environmental conditions whereas incidence of waterborne diseases decreases by 24% in housing societies where households have higher income, own water source or good water quality supplies and maintain personal hygiene[11].

Sourabh Paul, et. al, (2015), investigated jaundice outbreak in rural area of Odisha and analyzed that males were mostly affected. Cause of infection was use of water from open, shallow wells which got contaminated due to open defecation near water sources. Improper or less personal hygiene and lack of knowledge about prevention and control of hepatitis viral infection increase the spread of infectious diseases[12].

M.S.Sabeena Parvin, et. al, (2015), carried out study in Coimbatore district and concluded that water pollution is main cause of waterborne disease and therefore it creates scarcity of fresh water for drinking. Also observed people living in slum area suffers from waterborne diseases due to water logging and poor sanitation facilities and suggested that all available opportunities should be fully utilized in order to finish waterborne disease from its roots[13].

Sharma Mandakini, et. al, (2016), studied effect of water pollution on human health at Dehradun city and noticed that contamination of various toxics substance in water bodies have caused deterioration of water quality and developed waterborne diseases (diarrhea, typhoid and cholera), water washed disease(dysentery), water based disease(gastrointestinal), and water related vector borne disease(malaria)[14].

Dr Firdous Ansari, (2017), presented scenario of some waterborne disease in slums of Mumbai city and disclosed that 30% of all morbidity was accounted by water related infections such as jaundice, cholera, typhoid, malaria, intestinal. Cases of diarrheal was majorly reported. Age distribution of diarrheal cases was as follows 35% children under 5 years , 25% cases accounted for age group 5-18 years, 40%adults[15].

Manikandan R. et. al,(2017) analyzed water quality and treatment cost for waterborne disease in rural areas of Coimbatore district and revealed that available ground water was fit for domestic use also respondents benefited by purified supply of Aliyar dam water for drinking and domestic purpose are also safe from waterborne diseases.main cause of diseases include house service connections, stand post, overhead tank,irrigation well and springs[16].

Himadri Bhattacharjya,et. al,(2017), in West Tripur detected that 11% of ethnic and 8% of non-ethnic household collect water from sources which were highly contaminated with coli form organism and occurrence of diarrhea was high among households where coliform contamination of water was detected[17].

Sophia D.Fernandis,(2018), carried out community based cross sectional study to assess the drinking water handling practices and its association with waterborne disease at household level in tribal communityand found that 47.4% did not use any method of water disinfection whereas only 13% used boiling water and 40% used chlorination. The prevalence of waterborne disease was 81.57%and significantly associated with distance of drinking water source from house, education status, family type and knowledge and suggested that promotion and practice of hygienic water handling can reduce morbidity rate[18].

Antony Depa, et. al,(2018), assessed the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding food and waterborne disease among school children and depicted that teaching program for primary school would help to improve knowledge and follow healthy practices through which healthy generation can be built[19].

3. Conclusion:

High risk areas for waterborne diseases are rural and tribal areas and urban slums inhabited by the poor, marginalized and vulnerable groups with limited access to quality health care, communication and other basic amenities. Water borne diseases, such as Diarrhea, Dysentery, Cholera, Gastroenteritis are most common in above areas due to the contaminated drinking water associated with aerobic & anaerobic microbes. Poor habitat, improper sanitation and untreated drinking water from open sources like ponds, wells, rivers etc. are other major problems.

In urban areas lack of regular water supply drives people to store their water, and these water storage sites can become a breeding ground for microbes.

There is a substantial burden of waterborne diseases with risk factors not easily amenable to intervention. Although young children bear the greatest burden of diseases like cholera and diarrhea, all age groups are affected.

There is still concern about the availability of fresh and good quality drinking water to all Indians. If water supply, sanitation, hygiene and water resource management can be improved than at least 10 per cent of diseases worldwide could be avoided.

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